

Unusual negative selection pressure and lack of adaptation in SARS-CoV-2 ancestors

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Abstract

Measures of the proportion of non-synonymous to synonymous mutations such as dN/dS are used to estimate selection forces acting on a genome, gene, or smaller region of that gene. Here a simple ratio of synonymous to non-synonymous mutations is applied to pairs of sequences ancestral to SARS-CoV-2 and also to non-SARS-CoV-2 related control groups. This analysis reveals between some pairs of close ancestors, and SARS-CoV-2, an unexpectedly high proportion of synonymous mutations, suggesting negative selection – even despite the switch in host species and tissue tropism. This suggests a need for further investigation.

Introduction

Measures of the proportion of non-synonymous to synonymous mutations are used to estimate selection forces acting on a genome, gene, or smaller region of that gene. Generally a higher number of non-synonymous mutations is expected when selection pressure is positive. This would be expected when a virus is adapting to a new species, particularly in attachment proteins (such as spike in coronaviruses). Indeed in most SARS-Cov-2 variants, non-synonymous mutations vastly outweigh synonymous, though there are several interaction pressures at work – including those from vaccines and mAbs.

It is known that bats have greater immune tolerance to viruses and generate antibodies with lower affinity¹. So it might be expected that with less pressure from the immune system, a higher proportion of synonymous mutations might occur while viruses are evolving in bats. Even so, this pressure is not zero. A virus must continue to mutate to evade the immune system, even if already well-adapted to its host species.

Following the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, allegations have been made that the virus is artificial, and these should be investigated. If that was the case then we might expect some attempt to conceal the origin would be made. This could involve publishing fabricated sequence data (relatively simple to do) or even engineering artificial constructs (somewhat more difficult). In either case the objective would be to establish an evolutionary trail of viruses fraudulently claimed to have been found in nature. In designing such a sequence it would be relatively simple to incorporate synonymous mutations without disturbing the protein structure and potentially creating an unviable construct. This might result in an anomalously high proportion of synonymous mutations. Though unlikely to constitute definitive proof, this might have some value as a first step in investigations.

Method

The ratio of synonymous to non-synonymous mutations is calculated for the spike gene according to Nei and Gojobori, 1986² although without the Jukes Cantor correction. Calculations are based on a translation of the code from <https://www.hiv.lanl.gov/content/sequence/SNAP/SNAP.html> attributed to Korber, 2000³. The ratio I refer to as S/N is equivalent to Sd/Sn referenced at the webpage above.

Heatmaps are created based on code from

<https://sars2.net/scripts.html#Make a heatmap for ratio of synonymous to nonsynonymous mutations>. Somewhat arbitrarily, the scale was selected so that an S/N ratio of 7 is colored red (hottest).

Results

Control Groups

Control groups were selected from sequences that are not from the SARS-CoV-2 related clade.

UK Sarbecovs

UK SARS-CoV-1 related coronaviruses have been identified by 3 different groups⁴⁵⁶. They are all closely related, between them the lowest nucleotide identity in the spike is 97.3%.

African/European lineage sarbecovs

SARS-like coronaviruses of African/European lineage (including the UK groups) can be distinguished by having fewer deletions. Most pairs are relatively distant from each other, due no doubt to large geographic distance meaning this lineage is under-sampled. Some pairs published in 2021 by the Predict consortium⁷, including the viruses PRD-0038, PDF-2386/2370 (spike identical) S/N ratio that might be regarded as anomalously high.

Asian Lineage Sarbecovs

The source for many of these sequences (Rm1, Rp3, Rf1 and BtCoV-279) is the Wuhan Institute of Virology. They are relatively diverse in terms of geography and host species. Human SARS (Tor2 sequence) is included for reference.

Merbecovs

Bat MERS related sequences make an interesting control group for being sampled across a wide geographic region – China, HK, South Africa, Uganda, Switzerland, Russia and Italy are represented in the table. There are distinct lineages, and selection pressure is *generally* lower between more closely related sequences. Human MERS is included for reference.

Northern European Alphacoronaviruses

These were sampled in Finland, Russia and Denmark. The highest S/N ratio is 5.7 between a 98.9% identical pair.

HCov229E related coronaviruses.

Bats were sampled in Ghana by Corman et al (2015)⁸. Some 99.9% related sequences have been omitted from the table. Interestingly bat sequences have a higher S/N ratio compared to the more distant human sequences, than closely related human sequences do with each other. This is particularly so with the human reference sequence (shown as “229E”) which was sampled in 1973⁹. This is indicative of stronger pressure from the immune system promoting non-synonymous mutations. Other 229E sequences are from Chibo and Birch, 2006¹⁰.

SARS-CoV-2 related coronaviruses

ZC45 related coronaviruses

ZC45 and ZXC21 were the first SARS-CoV-2 related sequences to be published, by a team of PLA epidemiologists in March 2018¹¹, and were the only members of the new clade made public before the pandemic outbreak. Although they share common markers such as an identical Envelope gene with SARS-CoV-2, their RBD is closer to SARS-1 related covs, having characteristic deletions.

Some of the pairs here have S/N ratios that can only be described as alarmingly high. There are four viruses named Rp140346, Rs8561, Rs8572 and Rs8586 (the latter 3 have identical spike genes). Partial sequences including the spike gene were uploaded by Wuhan Institute of Virology to GenBank in July 2018, but remain in suppressed mode (accessions: MH615970, MH615971, MH615972, MH615973).

SARS-CoV-2 like coronaviruses

All of these sequences were published only after the pandemic outbreak. The first was RaTG13, published by Wuhan Institute of Virology¹². This was later superseded as closest to SARS-CoV-2 in spike by Banal-20-52¹³.

Included in the table is a hypothetical construct – either an artificial chimera or a natural recombinant composed of the spike of RaTG13, with the Receptor Binding Domain of Guangdong pangolin coronavirus MP789 substituted (amino acids 310 to 500 are replaced in the spike of RaTG13). This evolutionary path has been proposed by several authors¹⁴, and interestingly has the highest S/N ratio of any sequence compared to SARS-CoV-2 at 16. This construct is closer in amino acid sequence to SARS-CoV-2 than the closest known bat sequence (Banal-20-52), while having more synonymous mutations.

Banal-20-52 is itself extraordinary in having an S/N ratio of 9, but only 94.9% nucleotide identity with SARS-CoV-2 spike. A SNAP diagram of cumulative mutations shows it is exceptionally well conserved in the RBM, particularly given this pair represents at least one host switch, possibly via an intermediate species from a bat enteric virus, to a human respiratory one.

While RaTG13 has a more reasonable S/N ratio of 5.5, it is only due to the high proportion of non-synonymous mutations in the RBM.

If that RBM was substituted with a pangolin RBM then there are just 9 amino acid changes between Banal-20-52 and this hypothetical construct, but 218 synonymous mutations, a ratio of >24 to 1.

Banal-20-52 vs Chimera RaTG13/Pangolin

Accessions: UAY13217, S: 218 N: 9 I: 0 S/N: 24.22 N/S: 0.04

Further, it can be seen that the majority of amino acid changes are conservative substitutions. There is just one, Q789P, that would generally be regarded as non-conservative, and perhaps a second, N627D.

Banal-20-52 vs Chimera RaTG13/Pangolin

Accessions: UAY13217, S: 218 N: 9 I: 0 S/N: 24.22 N/S: 0.04

Discussion

Although it appears evident in the evolution of bat viruses that selection pressure is less than in human viruses, the evolution of SARS-CoV-2 related viruses is unlike that seen previously, in that evolution appears sometimes subject to exceedingly negative selection pressure. It is particularly remarkable that adaptation related to host switching is not evident.

In light of the circumstances of the pandemic, some consideration should be given to the possibility that viral sequences have been fabricated, or chimeric viruses engineered to conceal an artificial origin of SARS-CoV-2. If one were to fabricate a sequence based on another, it would be generally easier to make

synonymous changes in coding regions, which would have lower risk of creating a non-viable protein. Measures of the proportion of synonymous to non-synonymous mutations may thus be useful as an initial filter when investigating possible fraud.

Banal-20-52 is a particularly important sequence in establishing the origin of Covid-19, perceived as coming from an institution of high reputation. However, it is perhaps the most anomalous of all (aside from ZC45 related sequences) in terms of S/N ratios, and has an extremely close relationship to a recombinant which was initially propose. A deeper investigation into its provenance is warranted.

Data availability

Additional data

Additional charts and tables are available at:

<https://zenodo.org/records/14739207>

Genbank Accessions:

UK sarbecovs

OQ401252.2 RhGB08, OQ401249.1 RfGB02, OQ401247.1 RfGB01, OP776340.1 RhGB06, OP776339.1 RhGB05, OP837780.1 RhGB03, OQ401248.1 RhGB07, OP776338.1 RhGB02, OP837781.1 RhGB04, MW719567.1 RhGB01

229E related

DQ243972.1 HCoV-229E 1984, DQ243973.1 HCoV-229E 1990, DQ243984.1 HCoV-229E 2003, KY996417.1 229E/Florida/2016, KT253267.1 FO1E-F67, KT253265.1 KW1E-F12, KT253270.1 FO1A-F2, KT253261.1 FO-A-42, KT253269.1 KW2E-F151, NC_002645.1 HCoV 229E

North European alphacoronaviruses

OQ230639.1 RU/MOW15-23/2015, OP919651.1 RU/MOW15-21/2015, OR147948.1 RU/ROV21-132/4-Ped, MG923574.2 O20_16/FIN/16, MN482243.1 21164-6/DK/15, MN535733.1 OV-157/DK/18, MN535732.1 13585-58/DK/14, MZ218052.1 21164-6-alt/DK/15, MN535731.1 13585-35/DK/14, MN065811.1 008_16/FIN/16

Merbecovs

ON325306.1 MOW15-22, ON325308.1 V.murinus/SUI/2021, ON325307.1 V.murinus/SUI/2020, DQ648794.1 BtCoV/133/2005, MG596803.1 206645-63, MG596802.1 206645-40, KC869678.4 NeoCoV, EF065509.1 HKU5-1, EF065511.1 HKU5-3, EF065505.1 HKU4-1, EF065508.1 HKU4-4, NC_019843.3 MERS, NC_034440.1 PDF-2180

African/European coronaviruses

KR559017.1 BB9904, MW719567.1 RhGB01, KY352407.1 BtKY72, GU190215.1 BM48-31, MZ190138.1 Khosta-2, MZ190137.1 Khosta-1

East Asian sarbecovs

FJ588686.1 Rs672/2006, ON378802.1 B20-50, KU528591.1 B15-21, KY938558.1 16BO133, OR261262.1 RtVN21-29, NC_004718.3 SARS, DQ022305.2 HKU3-1, DQ071615.1 Rp3, DQ412043.1 Rm1, DQ412042 Rf1, DQ648857.1 BtCoV-279

ZC45 related

NC_045512.2 SARS-CoV-2, MG772933.1 ZC45, MG772934.1 ZXC21, MH615970.1 Rs8561_GD, MH615973.1 Rp140346_GD, OQ297706.1 GD/L102.18, KF294457.1 Longquan-140, MW532698.1 Pangolin GX

SARS-CoV02 related

MW532698.1 Pangolin GX, MT121216.1 Pangolin GD, MW251308.1 RacCS203, NMDC60013004-01 RmYN02, MN996532.2 RaTG13, MZ937004.1 BANAL-247, MZ937003.2 BANAL-236, MZ937002.1 BANAL-116, MZ937001.1 BANAL-103, MZ937000.1 BANAL-52

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